

NFDI4Cat: Repository software evaluation results

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NFDI4Cat project aims to establish a comprehensive research data infrastructure, a crucial task was to identify an appropriate software for the centralized repository capable of effectively storing and managing user data and metadata. This repository selection process was carried out by a thorough collection of user requirements, gathered through extensive interviews with project participants.

By consulting with a diverse range of stakeholders and experts, the NFDI4Cat project team was able to identify key criteria for the repository selection process. Once, the user requirements had been collected and analyzed, the project team was able to carefully evaluate potential repository options based on these criteria.

By selecting a centralized repository that meets the specific needs of project participants, the NFDI4Cat project is laying a solid foundation for the effective management and dissemination of research data. This infrastructure will not only benefit the project's immediate goals but also contribute to the larger research community by providing a valuable resource for storing and sharing data in a standardized and accessible way.

1 Introduction

Catalysis research has historically been hindered by a lack of digitization of research data, which has made it difficult to effectively share information and results among researchers in the field. This lack of sharing can slow down the pace of progress and limit the effectiveness of further development in the area. To address this issue, the primary goal of the project is to develop a comprehensive infrastructure for improving data management and ensuring the efficient life cycle of research data in catalysis. This infrastructure will include a centralized solution that conforms to the FAIR principles and is accessible to all project participants.

One essential component of the infrastructure will be a central repository where all data and metadata will be stored. This repository will enable researchers to easily access and share data in a standardized and structured format. By establishing this infrastructure, the project aims to facilitate collaboration and accelerate progress in catalysis research.

2 Methodology

To select the suitable repository, it is necessary to test several software products.

The preliminary stage of testing was the collection, processing and clarification of user requirements. These requirements were collected as a result of interviews with project participants and represented in the form of user stories. Furthermore, the requirements were tightly linked with different roles (Scientist, Administrator, Scientific Data Officer, Administrator/Developer, and External Scientist). All requirements were analysed and structured by epics, depending on the category and method of

application. After that, a document was created where all user requirements are presented in a structured form¹.

The most important provisions of the requirements are:

- Preserve research data in a FAIR way.
- The repository has to facilitate generic multipurpose storage and processing.
- The repository has to support various data formats.
- The repository has to support versioning of data.
- The repository has to provide a graphical user interface.
- The repository has to provide API.
- The central repository has to provide central and open storage.
- I want to be able to export data from the repository.
- I want to be able to publish data using the repository.
- I want to be able to manage data within the repository.
- The repository has to provide an interface for managing project data within a pre-existing data server.
- The repository has to provide analysis and visualization tools.
- I want to be able to explore data using the repository.
- I want to be able to create working spaces.

After analysing all the requirements, a quantitative assessment was carried out. It was carried out in several steps. At the first step, the priority of the requirement was determined. Priorities were assigned based on the importance for goals of the project and internal importance estimation. For those requirements that are most important to project users it was assigned "high" priority and quantitative value of 10. If a requirement had a "middle" priority, it was assigned a quantitative value of 3. For low priority requests it was assigned "low" priority and quantitative value of 1.

A similar approach in evaluating requirements and selecting software for the repository was applied in the project SDC4Lit². The advantage of this approach is that testing not only shows the final score, but also provides an opportunity to evaluate the functionality of the tested repositories in terms of the implemented requirements considering the given priority.

3 Software for repository

To assess the most suitable open source repository software package for the project, four software products were selected for testing: Dataverse (5.12.1), CKAN (2.9.7), DSpace (v.7), and InvenioRDM (v.9). These products are typically used for creating open access repositories for scholarly and/or published digital content.

Upon comparison of the architecture and technical descriptions of these products, it was found that they share a similar architecture, as detailed in the supplementary material. After this initial assessment, the next step was to install each of these products on virtual machines in bwCloud³. This cloud-based "infrastructure as a service" environment is specifically designed for research and teaching in Baden-Württemberg.

Throughout the testing process, particular attention was given to the key points that are most important for the project. These points include factors such as scalability, accessibility, and ease of

¹ Wentzel, Bianca, Schimmler, Sonja, Kushnarenko, Volodymyr, Petrenko, Taras, Huskova, Nadiia, Dikova, Yuliia, Rodrigues, Preston, Zhang, Yue, Doerr, Mark, Linke, David, & Bönisch, Thomas. (2023). NFDI4Cat: Requirements Analysis [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7729747>.

² Buck, Nina, Kushnarenko, Volodymyr, Schembera, Björn, Ulrich, Mona, Kramski, Heinz Werner, Ganzenmüller, Andreas, Hess, Jan, Holz, Alexander, Blessing, André, Hein, Pascal, Jung, Kerstin, Schenk, Nicolas, Schlesinger, Claus-Michael, Bönisch, Thomas, Kamzelak, Roland S., Kuhn, Jonas, & Viehhauser, Gabriel. (2023). How to choose a research data repository software? Experience report. Table of requirements. [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7656573>.

³ bwCloud. <https://www.bw-cloud.org/>, accessed on 05.05.2023.

use, as well as the ability to integrate with existing systems and comply with FAIR data principles. By carefully evaluating each of the repository solutions against these criteria, the project team will be better equipped to make an informed decision about which solution will be the most suitable for the project's needs.

Testing has shown that the order of loading a publication or experimental data is the same: the administrator creates a group or organization, the user logs in with his username and password and performs the necessary actions. To implement downloading or viewing downloaded materials, all repositories have an intuitive web interface.

Since several user groups were identified during the requirements analysis, as well as strictly limited access to downloads, groups and/or organizations, in the general case, several types of users were created for testing: administrator, simple user and guest. So, the administrator has all kinds of access rights to all groups, organizations and downloads. A simple user can have read access to all groups and/or organizations and full access to their group and/or organization. Guest mode provides read access only to specifically selected downloads.

However, this mode is not always acceptable. So, if a user with administrator rights requests access to another group, he automatically becomes the administrator of this group and will have full access rights, which is unacceptable in large projects. In this case, the access rights management mechanism provided by Dataverse implements all the necessary requirements, while the rest of the software under test does not.

Or a situation may arise when it is necessary to share the results of the experiment. In this case, the person who requested access to the data must have an account in the system or register. Ideally, there should be a mechanism for accessing unpublished or draft data, which provides for the absence of an account with third parties. However, only the Dataverse provides this opportunity by creating a Private URL⁴.

Special attention should be paid to working with metadata, since they play a key role in finding the necessary publications or experimental data. Each download must be described with metadata.

In all repositories, fields such as author, publication date, publication title are required. However, not all repositories have an extended set of primary metadata that would allow more detailed description of a publication. For example, in CKAN, the user can add an arbitrary number of additional fields by specifying the field name and its value. In Invenio and DSpace, the set of fields is limited and a detailed description is implemented using the "description" field. In Dataverse, it is possible to use dictionary-based metadata schemas⁵, which can significantly expand the amount of metadata involved.

Analysis of visualization tools showed that repositories provide previews for the most common formats such as txt, jpg, csv. Other formats require the installation of additional extensions.

4 Test results

As part of the testing process, the project team carefully assessed each requirement to determine the level of implementation that was feasible. For requirements that could be fully met without any additional actions, a weighting factor of one was assigned, based on the quantitative assessment of the requirement. In cases where additional actions, such as running a script, were needed to fully implement the requirement, the weight coefficient was set to 0.5. This indicates that the requirement was only partially implemented or requires additional actions from the user to be fully met. For requirements that were found to be unfeasible, the weighting coefficient was set to 0. This indicates

⁴ Dataverse, private URL to review unpublished dataset. <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/5.12.1/user/dataset-management.html?highlight=privat%20url>, accessed on 05.05.2023.

⁵ Dataverse, metadata customization. <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/admin/metadatacustomization.html>, accessed on 05.05.2023.

that the requirement could not be met within the scope of the project, and alternative solutions would need to be explored.

The testing process has shown that certain requirements, such as visualization or data preview, cannot be met with an out-of-the-box installation of the software product. In this case, the solution was sought by installing additional extensions, the installation of which will automatically implement the necessary requirement. With this approach, the requirement was also considered fully realizable.

According to this, the general test results are as follows:

- Total amount of requirements (user stories) – 60 (max 521 score points possible).
- Requirements with the priority "high" – 49.
- Requirements with the priority "middle" – 10.
- Requirements with the priority "low" – 1.

Table 1 presents the results of testing each group of requirements for the selected software products.

Table 1. Results of software evaluation from user perspective

Priority	DSpace		Dataverse		CKAN		InvenioRDM	
	Amount	Points	Amount	Points	Amount	Points	Amount	Points
Fully realizable "high"	40	400	43	430	39	390	40	400
Fully realizable "middle"	7	21	6	18	7	21	5	15
Fully realizable "low"	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Partly realizable "high"	8	40	3	15	9	45	6	30
Partly realizable "middle"	1	1,5	1	1,5	1	1,5	2	3
Partly realizable "low"	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Non realizable "high"	1	0	3	0	2	0	3	0
Non realizable "middle"	2	0	3	0	2	0	3	0
Non realizable "low"	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Overall		463,5		465,5		458,5		449

As can be seen from the Table 1, Dataverse scored the most points obtained when testing user requirements.

In addition to the user requirements collected as a result of the interviews, there were requirements from the administrative perspective. They took into account criteria such as:

- Simplicity of installation process, reliability of base functionality with future updates, community support, availability of documentation. This requirement was evaluated as follows: 1 – simple installation, Guides available, active Community; 0.5 – additional technical support needed; 0 - no guides, difficult installation process.
- The need to install additional extensions – the more additional extensions are required to fulfil the requirements, the more complex the system becomes. If a large number of additional extensions were required, the score is 0; 0.5 – extensions needed partly; 1 – without any additional extensions.

- User rights (manipulation with user rights). This requirement was evaluated as follows: 0 – strict set of roles; 0.5 – different roles; 1 – the ability to assign a different role for the same user.
- Private link for unpublished publications. 0 – impossible share data/datasets with private link; 1 – possible share data/datasets with private link.
- Different metadata schemes. 0 – there is no fields for primary metadata; 0.5 – limited set of primary metadata; 1 – flexible metadata schemes.

5 Conclusion

Thus, according to user requirements, Dataverse has the most points (465.5). According to administrative requirements Dataverse also has the most points (45)⁶. Common result shows that Dataverse (total points = 510.5) is the most suitable candidate for the central repository.

Based on the results obtained for the central repository, it was decided to choose Dataverse as the software. However, it is worth noting that there are a number of problems when testing and choosing software:

- It is not possible to cover 100% of requirements (user stories) - additional implementation will be needed.
- Repositories do not provide an ability to export all or selected publications directly from the database. Custom scripts for that are needed.
- Additional extensions required to ensure analytical, statistical and visualisation capabilities
- Limited functionality with metadata (Linked Data usually is not supported).
- Repositories do not provide interfaces for working with SPARQL.
- Previewers usually support only the most common data formats (image formats, pdf, csv, etc...) – for specific formats additional extensions are needed.
- Complex implementation of communication between the central repository and existing local systems and software products – integrating the already available pilot systems of our partners with the central repository into the new created NFDI4Cat infrastructure will be the next challenge.

In the future, it is planned to install the selected software, search for software solutions to minimize and/or eliminate the above given problems, and launch a project for a comprehensive assessment of the performance of the full set of selected tools.

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⁶ For more details, please, see slide with additional requirements in presentation.